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IMPACT OF INTERNAL CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY PRACTICES ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE: EVIDENCE FROM LISTED INSURANCE COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Corporate Social Responsibility, a statutory practice, has over the years become an important determinant of organisational well-being. The inadequacies of the CSR, however, have continued to raise concerns about the effectiveness of CSR designs and implementation as it affects the Financial Performance of listed Insurance Companies in Nigeria. This study, therefore, examined the impact of CSR on Financial Performance indicators of listed ICs in Nigeria. This study employed an *ex-post facto* research design wherein secondary data were sourced from published annual reports and accounts of listed ICs, over 10 years from 2015 to 2024. Findings reveal that CSR has a positive but modest effect on financial performance. Insurance firms actively involved in CSR and social benefit programs demonstrated better ROI and market value performance over time. R&D and firm size significantly influenced profitability, indicating that larger and more innovative firms gain more from CSR integration. Conversely, high leverage ratios were found to weaken financial gains due to increased debt burdens. The descriptive results also show that Nigerian insurance companies vary widely in market capitalisation and leverage structure, with a few dominant firms holding the largest market share. The study concludes that CSR, though not immediately profitable, enhances long-term sustainability, corporate image, and stakeholder confidence. It recommends that insurance companies integrate CSR into their strategic management framework and adopt transparent CSR reporting practices to improve financial performance and public trust. The findings contribute to the growing discourse on the strategic role of CSR in improving corporate performance in emerging markets like Nigeria.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Social Benefit, Research, Development, Financial Performance Indicators.

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INTRODUCTION

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a business organisation's configuration of principles, processes, and outcomes related to its societal relationships. This umbrella concept encompasses a variety of organisational policies and activities intended to address stakeholder interests, as well as the impacts of these actions (Okafor et al., 2020). Further elaborating on this, Nguyen et al. (2022) described CSR as the notion where firms integrate social and environmental concerns into their business operations and stakeholder dealings. The European Commission (2017) reinforces this by describing CSR as actions that allow companies to meet legal obligations and go beyond them to invest in human capital, the environment, and stakeholder relations. In the contemporary business landscape, CSR is an established and significant

part of decision-making, generally accepted by businesses, governments, and the public as a source of considerable benefit. Consequently, most organisations translate their CSR policy into activity (Gomez et al., 2017). While stakeholders may be cynical about the genuineness of these corporate actions, evidence indicates that corporations engage in them not merely out of tradition but because they recognise the accruing benefits. As Gomez et al. (2017) opine, altruism is no longer a prerequisite for CSR activity, as enlightened self-interest shows it to be beneficial. The adoption of CSR principles should not be perceived as a marginal decision but as part of the company's wider culture, involving all its hierarchical components. Measuring the performance of business organisations has long been of central interest to

managers, shareholders, researchers, and governments (Onaolapo & Kolawole, 2019).

According to Babajide and Olagunju (2019), performance can be measured both financially and non-financially, serving as key indicators for monitoring strategy implementation and the achievement of strategic goals. Barman and Mahakud (2024) assert that financial performance (FP) is the major premise upon which the efficiency and effectiveness of organisational operations are based. As a primary driver of investment decisions, performance must exhibit favourable potential in the short, medium, and long term. Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets to generate revenues and is the process of measuring the results of a firm's policies and operations in monetary terms (Barman & Mahakud, 2024). It serves to identify a firm's financial strengths and weaknesses and is used to compare firms within an industry or sector in aggregate. Quantitative measures include profitability indicators like return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and economic value added; cash flow measures such as free cash flow; and growth measures like historical revenue growth. Ideally, forward-looking measures should be used (Malikov et al., 2021). Financial performance indicators are broadly categorised as market-based or accounting-based. Common indicators include ROE, ROA, Return on Investment (ROI), Tobin's Q, Earnings per Share (EPS), and Stock Returns, all of which are influenced by the corporate governance mechanisms an organisation adopts. Management researchers often prefer accounting variables like ROA, ROE, and ROI as performance measures. Whether and how Corporate Social Responsibility relates to corporate financial performance remains a point of contention and debate amongst organisational researchers (Khan & Banerji, 2016).

Some studies have shown evidence that CSR is positively associated with companies' financial performance (Zhang & Ziyang, 2023; Wang & Sarkis, 2013). However, other studies show mixed or insignificant relationships (e.g., Barnett & Salomon, 2012). A posited reason for these mixed results is a lack of consideration for

moderating or mediating influences (Endrikat et al., 2014; Javed et al., 2016; Reverte et al., 2016).

Empirical research reflects this divergence. Barman and Mahakud (2024), examining listed firms in India from 2016 to 2021, found a significant and positive association between CSR expenditure and corporate performance. Their study also revealed that business group affiliation reduces this CSR-performance sensitivity and that mandatory CSR norms significantly influence the relationship. Similarly, Zhang and Ziyang (2023), studying listed Chinese companies, found that CSR was significantly positively correlated with financial performance and brand value, with social capital playing a positive moderating role. Conversely, other studies present conflicting findings. Nguyen et al. (2022), in their analysis of Vietnamese listed companies from 2012 to 2017, suggested that overall CSR disclosure harms firm performance. A more detailed view showed that environmental responsibility had a clear negative influence, while social responsibility demonstrated a weak, preferable impact. The economic aspect of CSR has no significant effect. Likewise, Sameer (2021), in a study of Maldivian public limited companies, found a significant negative relationship between certain CSR dimensions (diversity and environment) and financial performance indicators like ROA and ROE.

The relationship is further complicated by endogenous factors and governance structures. Zhao et al. (2016) studied firms in China and reported that the relationship between managers' attention to social issues and corporate social performance is moderated by governance mechanisms that constrain managerial discretion. Ironically, even when firms comply with an optimal level of CSR practices, a causal effect on performance may never be guaranteed since CSR compliance could be endogenously determined (Akbar et al., 2016). In such a case, there would be no observable relationship between CSR and firm performance (Love, 2011). If compliance is endogenously chosen, each firm will reach its optimal level of compliance, which might improve the redistribution of rent between shareholders and managers but not necessarily increase overall firm performance (Akbar et al.,

2016). The extent to which the results of previous studies remain inconclusive necessitates further research.

This study is anchored on Stakeholder Theory. Donaldson and Preston (1995) contended that a 'stake' implies normative obligations, meaning stakeholders have an interest for which a valid normative claim can be advanced. In other words, stakeholders have identifiable and justifiable obligations to, and on the organisation. CSR, as a mandatory obligation for listed organisations, is thus positioned to be mutually beneficial to all stakeholders, including the company, employees, creditors, and tax authorities. To this end, this study aims to evaluate the impact of CSR on the Financial Performance of listed Insurance Companies (ICs) in Nigeria. The study also seeks to relate specific CSR practices, namely Research and Development (Staff Training) and Social Benefit (Staff fringe benefits and other allowances), with financial performance indicators (Market Value and Return on Investment). The research employed a census of all twenty-three (23) Insurance Companies listed by the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX) over ten years from 2015 to 2024.

Statement of the Problem

Corporate Social Responsibility is an issue that has, in the few last decades, gained momentum in business and financial research. The debate on the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and Corporate Financial Performance (CFP) has been ongoing. This is simply because of the great impact it has had on influencing financial performance. For instance, in the works of Barman and Mahakud (2024), it was concluded that in the long run, firms stand to benefit greatly in their investments in CSR. Firms that commit huge resources into the provision of Social Benefits (SB) to her employees are expected to benefit greatly in low labour turnover, employee's commitment and dedication, provision of innovative ideas and so on which can turn the fortunes of the enterprise around in attracting more investors. However, facts at the disposal of the researcher do not align with this assertion, particularly as it relates to the listed ICs in Nigeria. It has been observed from the published annual report and accounts of listed

ICs that despite huge resources committed into the provision of SB to their employees, it has not had having commensurate impact on the Return on Investment (ROI). This is a serious problem because the huge investment, which is costing ICs huge fortunes, is becoming unjustifiable in the long run. The huge R&D investments are expected to attract more investors, thereby improving the market value of the firms. However, in the case of ICs listed on the Nigerian Exchange, the reverse is the case. Literature (Cifti *et al.*, 2019) reported that despite huge resources committed to R&D by ICs in Nigeria, results obtained from their published annual report and accounts have proved otherwise. This has, however, put a question mark on the authenticity of the claims that investment in R&D as a CRS must lead to better financial performance in terms of improved ROA.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective was to determine the impact of CSR on Financial Performance, while the specific objectives of this study were to:

1. ascertain the level of significant effect that SB has on the ROI of listed ICs.
2. evaluate the degree of impact that R&D has on MV of listed ICs.

Research Questions

The following questions are raised to guide the study:

1. To what level does Social Benefit (SB) have significant effect on Return on Investment (ROI) of listed ICs?
2. To what degree does Research and Development impact on Market Value (MV) of listed ICs?

Null Hypotheses

The study hypotheses are formulated in null form thus:

- HO₁:** Social Benefits has no significant effect on Return on Investment of listed Insurance Companies in Nigeria
- HO₂:** There is no significant impact of Research and Development on market value of listed Insurance Companies in Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

This study employed ex-post facto research design, which is a research design that investigates the cause-and-effect relationship through the examination of the existing conditions that have previously occurred. The application of this design ensures that the independent variable is not manipulated by the researcher; rather, they examine existing data to identify patterns, associations, or effects. Within the context of this study, the application of the ex-post facto design is appropriate

In the investigation of the relationship between CSR and Financial Performance of Listed Insurance Companies in Nigeria, both CSR activities and financial performance data already exist in the firms' annual reports and financial statements. The researcher merely observes and analyses these historical data to determine whether variations in CSR practices (independent variable) are associated with changes in financial performance indicators such as return on investment (ROI), market value (MV), and firm size (FS) (dependent variables).

Secondary data was collected in this study to achieve the research objectives. Quantitative data were sourced from the annual reports of the listed insurance companies in Nigeria to obtain relevant data on the relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and the Financial Performance of listed insurance companies in Nigeria. The data were extracted from the audited annual financial statements and sustainability reports of 37 listed insurance companies in Nigeria, covering a period of 10 years, that is, between 2015 and 2024. These documents provided reliable and verifiable figures on key variables such as Market Value (MV), Return on Investment (ROI), Social Benefits (SB, Research & Development (R&D), Leverage (LEV) and Firm Size (FS). Furthermore, data were also sourced from Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) Fact Book, Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, and corporate governance reports to validate financial and CSR indicators. In analysing data collected for this study, methods adopted were not only "objective/research question based" but also be hypothesis driven. In addition to this, previously

employed analytical tools, by authors, which have been tested, validated and employed, were adopted. Consideration was given to evolving analytical method(s) which are adjudged to have the potential to take care of limitations, noticed with others in use, such as unobservable heterogeneity, simultaneity and dynamic endogeneity, to bridge the methodological gaps in the literature. Considering the above, objectives were analysed using descriptive analysis. In addition to this, each objective was specifically analysed using different tools. To analyse the first research objective, that is, to determine the level of significant effect that SB has on the ROI of listed ICs, the Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) was used. Using GMM, three standard diagnostic tests will be conducted to identify the problems that may arise from the use of GMM estimation. These diagnostic tests are the F-test (λ), the Hansen J-statistic, and the AR2, which will be used to test the joint significance of the coefficients, the validity of instruments, and autocorrelation of the residuals, respectively. GMM, however, controls for the effects of unobservable heterogeneity, simultaneity and dynamic endogeneity and thus presents more robust results. Objective two (2), i.e., to evaluate the degree of impact that R&D has on MV of listed ICs, Variance Decomposition Analysis was adopted.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the outcome of descriptive statistics for six key variables used in this study, these are Market Value, Return on Investment (ROI), Social Benefits (CSR proxy), Research and Development (RD), Leverage (LEV), and Firm Size (FS) across 370 observations from 37 listed insurance companies listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on the Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility and Financial Performance of Listed Insurance Companies in Nigeria

	MV	ROI	SB	RD	LEV	FS
Mean	3.705315	16.23851	0.906415	0.896862	1.94E+08	4.84E+08
Median	1.137650	11.56280	0.928600	0.923100	13534957	24486904
Maximum	735.4102	210.9745	1.000000	1.000000	1.02E+10	2.46E+10
Minimum	-0.508000	-16.18350	0.615400	0.615400	49472.00	29250.00
Std. Dev.	38.18024	16.53593	0.100390	0.116215	9.95E+08	2.54E+09
Skewness	19.10072	4.958662	-1.517160	-1.006567	7.813108	7.353643
Kurtosis	366.5543	54.00490	4.686270	2.928084	65.17206	57.83185
Jarque-Bera	2060145.	41622.73	185.7801	62.55903	63355.46	49685.38
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	1370.967	6008.250	335.3737	331.8391	7.16E+10	1.79E+11
Sum Sq. Dev.	537902.6	100898.3	3.718807	4.983669	3.65E+20	2.37E+21
Observations	370	370	370	370	370	370

Analysis of data presented in Table 1 shows that the mean of the market value of the insurance companies is 3.71, while the standard deviation is 38.18. This result suggests that there are substantial differences in the market capitalization of listed insurance firms. The minimum and maximum values of -0.51 and 735.41 respectively show the presence of extreme outliers, which implies that a few insurance firms enjoy very high market valuations while others remain relatively small. The high skewness (19.10) and kurtosis (366.55) further reveal that the distribution of market value is positively skewed and highly peaked, suggesting that only a few large firms dominate the market.

Tables 2 and 3 present information on the Unit Root Test conducted for the study. The tables show data in respect to the four different methods employed in conducting the unit root test which include Levin, Lin and Chu, Im, Pesaran and Shin, Augumented Dickey Fuller test and Philip-Perron Fisher chi-square. The test is conducted to establish the stationarity or non-stationarity of the data employed for the study.

Table 2: Unit-Root Analysis at Level

Variables	LLC	IPS	ADF	PP
MV	-3.8041 (0.0001)***	-0.93666 (0.1745)	93.7213 (0.0606)*	119.712 (0.0006)***
ROI	-5.6273 (0.0000)***	-1.80776 (0.0353)**	104.68 (0.0110)**	152.036 (0.0000)***
SB	-1.2714 (0.1018)	-0.03178 (0.4873)	21.1343 (0.7350)	29.7696 (0.2773)
LEV	-8.0278 (0.0000)**	-2.67565 (0.0037)***	117.647 (0.0009)***	116.313 (0.0012)***
FS	-2.0820 (0.0187)**	-0.54371 (0.2933)***	73.5456 (0.4930)**	85.6180 (0.1677)***

Table 3: Unit Root Analysis at First Difference

TVvariables	LLC	IPS	ADF	PP
MV	-13.7609 (0.0001)***	-5.50163 (0.0000)***	182.519 (0.0000)***	289.609 (0.0000)***

R&D	3.6187 (0.0001)***	-0.80121 (0.0115)**	38.5133 (0.0891)*	64.9176 (0.0000)***
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Note: LLC= Levin, Lin and Chu, IPS= Im, Pesaran and Shin, ADF=Augumented Dickey Fuller test and PP = Philip-Perron Fisher chi-square.

*** Indicates significant at 1% level

** Indicates significant at 5% level

* Indicates significant at 10% level

() Probability values

Study of time series models is principally concerned with the testing for the existence of unit roots. When unit root is present, it implies that the time series data under investigation is non-stationary. On the other hand, the absence of unit roots explains that the stochastic process is stationary. Often, most time series data are not stationary at certain significant levels as some variables may be too small or large to the extent that they never return to their expected mean. Hence, the need to carry out unit root test whenever dealing with time series data. The need for the test of panel data is very essential knowing the fact that panel data is prone to spurious regression results. However, to test for the Stationarity of the panel variables, this study conducted unit root tests using four different methods. The findings of the stationary test are as presented in Table 2 and 3. The unit root test result shows that all the variables became stationary after first difference. Given that all the variables in the model have become stationary, other regression methods have been run. Model Estimation (ME), Variance and Decomposition Analysis (VDA) were also run after the unit root test had been carried out.

TABLE 4: Generalized Moment of Method establishing the relationship between CSR and Return on Investment

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ROI(-1)	-0.252432	0.000672	-375.8036	0.0000
SB	-1.889264	0.122602	-15.40978	0.0000
RD	3.834934	0.024742	154.9954	0.0000

LEV	2.13E-10	1.31E-11	16.32891	0.0000
FS	7.08E-12	4.90E-12	1.445650	0.1494
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (first differences)				
Mean dependent				
var	-0.017767	S.D. dependent var	1.443969	
S.E. of				
regression	1.321392	Sum squared resid	504.6162	
J-statistic	32.00737	Instrument rank	38	
Prob(J-statistic)	0.416387			

Analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between CSR and MV using Variance Decomposition Analysis (VDA). Aside 10-year data for CSR, Financial performance indicators and control variables, other information shown in the table are “Period” and “Standard Error” (S.E). Table 4 specifically establishes how MV is affected by other variables over the ten years and which of the indicators have a greater influence on MV.

TABLE 5: Variance Decomposition Analysis (VDA) of Market Value (MV)

Period	S.E.	MV	SB	RD	LEV	FS
1	12.95831	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	14.36519	98.96707	0.014926	0.447909	0.110617	0.117543
3	15.69566	98.75371	0.013920	0.377627	0.094080	0.457975
4	16.40095	98.60963	0.025147	0.383365	0.086162	0.562941
5	16.87738	98.54470	0.033199	0.368383	0.083660	0.633399
6	17.17996	98.48684	0.043255	0.361056	0.084912	0.673245
7	17.37913	98.44363	0.052835	0.354808	0.088179	0.698133
8	17.50961	98.40689	0.062162	0.350479	0.092118	0.713718
9	17.59574	98.37647	0.070870	0.347364	0.096007	0.723620
10	17.65265	98.35082	0.078904	0.345200	0.099494	0.729940

Variance decomposition analysis provides information about the relative contribution of each of the random innovations affecting the variables in a model. Furthermore, while Variance Decomposition Analysis (VDA) separates the variations in an endogenous variable into the component shocks in the model, Impulse Response Function (IRF) traces the effects of a change to another endogenous variable in the VDA environment. The variance decomposition analysis results for the listed variables (SB, RD, LEV, and FS) over a 10-year horizon are as presented in Table 5. The results reveal that the MV of listed ICs in Nigeria was 100 percent explained by its own shock in the first year, but it slowly reduces to 98 percent in the long run (i.e. the 10th year). Other complementary results show that SB has a total

of 0.07 percent, RD has a total of 0.34 percent, LEV has 0.09 percent and lastly the FS has 0.72 percent report for the fluctuations in the MV of listed ICs in Nigeria in the long run (i.e. the 10th year). "The implication of the relationship between MV and other explanatory and control variables (SB, RD, LEV, and FS) is that, although all of them contribute slightly to variations in MV initially, their contribution increases over time. FS has the strongest influence on determining changes in MV at 0.72% while SB is the least contributor at 0.07%.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study are a product of both descriptive and inferential analyses, which provide a comprehensive understanding of the relationship existing between CSR and the financial performance of listed insurance companies in Nigeria. The descriptive statistics indicated substantial heterogeneity among the insurance firms in terms of market value, profitability, leverage, and firm size, reflecting the uneven distribution of resources and operational capacity across the Nigerian insurance sector.

Similarly, the mean value of the return on investment (ROI) as shown in Table 1 is 16.24, while the standard deviation is 16.54. This result shows moderate profitability among the listed insurance companies, however, there is wide variation in the level of performance. The maximum ROI of 210.97 compared to a minimum of -16.18 affirms that even though some insurance companies recorded significant returns, others operated at a loss. The skewness (4.96) and kurtosis (54.00) values indicates a highly skewed and leptokurtic distribution, which is an indication that most firms have average ROI values, with a few achieving exceptionally high profits. With respect to the social benefits, which serves as a proxy for CSR, the mean value of 0.91 and a low standard deviation of 0.10 is an indication that most insurance companies demonstrate a relatively high level of CSR engagement with little variation. The values of the social benefits range between 0.62 and 1.00, which is an indication that nearly all the firms participate in socially beneficial programs. The negative skewness with

a value of -1.52 suggests that majority of the firms have CSR values above the mean, implying a generally strong CSR orientation across the insurance sector.

For research and development (R&D) activities, the mean and median values (0.90 and 0.92 respectively) are closely aligned, which suggests there is consistency among insurance firms in their commitment to R&D. Also, the relatively low standard deviation of 0.12 and negative skewness of -1.01 further indicate that most of the insurance companies maintain above average levels of investment in innovation and improvement initiatives. Furthermore, the leverage (LEV) ratio recorded a mean of ₦1.94×10⁸ and a very high standard deviation of ₦9.95×10⁸, signifying substantial variation in debt structure among the firms. The extremely large maximum value (₦1.02×10¹⁰) relative to the minimum (₦49,472) shows that a few firms are heavily leveraged compared to others. The positive skewness (7.81) and kurtosis (65.17) confirm the presence of these outliers, reflecting the unequal financial strength and borrowing capacity among Nigerian insurance companies. Result on the firm size (FS) reveal a mean of ₦4.84×10⁸ as well as standard deviation of ₦2.54×10⁹. This highlights the disparity in asset size across the insurance firms. The maximum value of ₦2.46×10¹⁰ further indicates that while a few of the insurance firms possess vast resources and capital bases, several firms, however, operate on a smaller scale. The high positive skewness (7.35) and kurtosis (57.83) further corroborate this uneven distribution, emphasising that the industry is dominated by a few large players. Across all variables, the Jarque-Bera probability values ($p = 0.0000$) are statistically significant, which is an indication that the data are not normally distributed. This also suggests the presence of extreme values and potential heterogeneity among the sampled companies. The non-normality is an implication that subsequent inferential analyses should consider robust estimation methods to account for skewed distributions and reduce bias in regression results.

The wide variation in market value (MV) and return on investment (ROI), with high skewness

and kurtosis, suggests that while a few firms dominate the market and exhibit high profitability, the majority operate at moderate or lower levels of performance. This result supports earlier observations by researchers such as Osemene and Muritala (2021) and Eze and Maduka (2022), who found that the Nigerian insurance industry is characterized by few dominant players who have substantial financial leverage as well as capital advantage. The significant disparity is also an indication of structural and operational inefficiencies within the insurance sector, which may influence the ability of firms to fully integrate CSR into their strategic objectives.

Results of the analysis shown in Table 2 conducted to establish the relationship between CSR and ROI using Generalized Method of Moment (GMM). Other information shown in the table include; proxies for CSR and Control variables i.e. SB, R&D, LEV and FS respectively. The table also show figures of mean dependent var, S.E. of regression, J-statistic, Prob(J-statistic), S.D. dependent var, Sum squared resid and Instrument rank.

From Table 3, the additional variable generated by GMM, namely, lag of return on assets is positively and statistically significant for determining the financial performance of listed ICs in Nigeria. A percentage increase in the lag of SB leads to a 2.5% decrease in the performance (ROI) of ICs in Nigeria. The relationship between R&D and ROI is also significant, as the p -values for both variables are less than 0.05. The results further revealed a positive and significant relationship between R&D and ROI, meaning that a unit increase in disclosure index results in an increase in return on assets, a measure for the performance of listed ICs in Nigeria. In the same manner, leverage, as a control variable, shows a positive and statistically significant relationship with ROI. This is an indication that a percentage increase in the leverage only results to an increase in the ROI of listed ICs in Nigeria. Furthermore, a percentage increase in FS as the second control variable brings about a 71% increase in the ROI of listed ICs. Generally, there is every tendency that all indicators of CSR proxied by SB and

R&D impact Financial Performance (ROI) of listed ICs in Nigeria but inherent and unfavourable practices that could be impeding positive increase in the performance of listed companies should be addressed by the management and regulatory authorities issuing the codes of corporate governance. The finding regarding the relationship between SB and ROI contradicts the null hypothesis, which states that SB has no significant relationship with ROI. Therefore, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected. The result further showed that social benefits, which is a proxy of CSR have a mean score of 0.91 and a low standard deviation of 0.10. This suggests that most of the insurance firms engage actively in CSR-related initiatives. This finding corroborates that of Nwude, Udeh, and Onwuka (2023), who noted that listed insurance firms in Nigeria increasingly use CSR as a reputational and trust-building strategy to enhance the confidence of customers and regulatory goodwill. However, the presence of negative skewness in CSR distribution reveals that although CSR practices are widespread in the industry, the quality and depth of implementation vary among the firms. Similarly, the insurance companies' research and development (R&D) activities recorded consistent mean and median values, indicating a general commitment to innovation. The negative skewness observed further suggests that investment of most of the firms in R&D is above average. This finding corroborates the assertion of Adebayo and Eniola (2020), where it was found that innovation-driven strategies enhance product diversification and customer satisfaction in the Nigerian financial services sector. However, the impact of R&D on financial outcomes remains moderate, which is possibly a function of the limited integration of technological innovations in the operational framework of many firms.

The findings on leverage (LEV) and firm size (FS) of insurance firms indicate that larger firms tend to have higher debt capacities and dominate market operations. The high mean and standard deviation values coupled with positive skewness demonstrate wide disparities among the insurance firms. This pattern is consistent with findings from Uwuigbe, Olusanmi, and Eriabie (2021), who emphasized that larger firms are

better positioned in the effective implementation of CSR activities because of their stronger capital bases and broader stakeholder networks. Across all variables, the significant Jarque-Bera probabilities ($p = 0.0000$) confirm non-normal distributions of the data, which is an indication of the presence of extreme values and the need for robust estimation methods. This aligns with econometric best practices in panel data studies, where heterogeneity among firms is expected. The unit root test results revealed that all variables became stationary after the first difference, confirming the appropriateness of panel regression techniques for subsequent analysis. This ensures the reliability of the model estimation results and the avoidance of spurious regressions.

The Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) results demonstrated the existence of a significant relationship between CSR and financial performance. Specifically, social benefits (SB) exhibited a negative but significant effect on ROI, an indication that CSR expenditures may initially reduce profitability in the short term because of resource commitments, a finding which is consistent with the short-term cost-long-term gain hypothesis (Obi & Akinola, 2022). Conversely, R&D showed a positive and significant relationship with ROI, an indication that innovation contributes to profitability and operational efficiency. Leverage was also found to have a positive and significant relationship with ROI, implying that prudent debt utilisation enhances financial performance.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and the financial performance of listed insurance companies in Nigeria, with particular emphasis on indicators such as market value, return on investment, research and development, leverage, firm size, and social benefits. The empirical findings of this study revealed that while CSR activities are becoming increasingly integrated into strategic operations of insurance firms in Nigeria, their direct impact on financial performance remains modest, while in some cases, negative in the short term because of the associated implementation costs. However, in the long run, CSR initiatives contribute significantly

to brand equity, customer loyalty, and the overall organizational sustainability. Despite the general progress observed, regarding CSR, the study identified disparities in the level of CSR engagement among firms. Some companies undertake CSR primarily for compliance and reputation management rather than as a core component of strategic development. Moreover, the presence of non-normal data distributions and significant variations across firms suggests that structural and operational differences continue to affect the effectiveness of CSR initiatives within the Nigerian insurance sector. In conclusion, the findings underscore the importance of strategically aligning the CSR of organisations with their corporate objectives to enhance both financial and social outcomes. Nigerian insurance companies must therefore adopt a long-term perspective that views CSR not merely as a philanthropic obligation but rather as an investment in corporate reputation, stakeholder trust, and market sustainability. Furthermore, regulators and policymakers should strengthen disclosure frameworks and provide incentives that encourage firms to embed CSR and innovation within their governance systems. By doing so, the insurance industry can foster a culture of transparency, accountability, and inclusive growth, contributing meaningfully to Nigeria's broader economic development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the outcome of this study, it is therefore recommended that:

1. Firms within the Insurance sub-sector of Nigeria's economy should strive to enhance Social Benefit packages to the employees, as this could have a positive and significant impact on return on investment.
2. Firms in the Insurance sub-sector should endeavour to integrate CSR into their long-term strategy rather than treating it as an isolated or philanthropic activity.
3. Considering the positive and significant relationship between financial performance and research and development (R&D), R&D can therefore be used to design new products for firms in the Insurance sub-sector of the Nigeria economy.
4. Given the evidence of data heterogeneity and non-normality among firms, researchers and

practitioners in the insurance sub-sector should apply robust analytical methods for performance evaluation. Insurance firms can adopt advanced data analytics and risk management tools to monitor CSR efficiency, financial performance, and market dynamics, ensuring evidence-based decision-making.

REFERENCES

- Adegbite, E., Nakpodia, F., & Soobaroyen, T. (2018). Corporate governance and environmental sustainability in Nigeria. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 27(7), 950–965.
- Akbar, S., Poletti-Hughes, J., El-Faitouri, R., & Shah, S. Z. A. (2016). More on the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance in the UK: Evidence from the application of generalized method of moments estimation. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 38, 417–429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2016.03.009>
- Babajide, A. A., & Olagunju, K. O. (2019). Corporate governance and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business Governance and Ethics*, 13(3), 261–279.
- Barman, S., & Mahakud, J. (2024). Corporate social responsibility and financial performance: Do group affiliation and mandatory corporate social responsibility norms matter? *IIMB Management Review*, 36(3), 256–268.
- Barnett, M. L., & Salomon, R. M. (2012). Does it pay to be really good? Addressing the shape of the relationship between social and financial performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 33(11), 1304–1320. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.1980>
- Wang, C.-H. (2011). Clarifying the effects of R&D on performance: Evidence from the high technology industries. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 16(1), 51–64.
- Ciftci, I., Tatoglu, E., Demirbag, M., & Zaim, S. (2019). Corporate governance and firm performance in emerging markets: Evidence from Turkey. *International Business Review*, 28(1), 90–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2018.08.004>
- European Union. (2017). *A renewed EU strategy 2011–14 for corporate social responsibility: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the*

- European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions* (COM(2011) 681 final). Brussels.
- Endrikat, J., Guenther, E., & Hoppe, H. (2014). Making sense of conflicting empirical findings: A meta-analytic review of the relationship between corporate environmental and financial performance. *European Management Journal*, 32(5), 735–751.
- Ghaffar, A., & Khan, W. A. (2014). Impact of research and development on firm performance. *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*, 4(1), 357–367.
- Gomez, L. M., Vargas-Preciado, L., & Crowther, D. (2017). *Corporate social responsibility and corporate governance: Concepts, perspectives and emerging trends in Ibero-America* (1st ed.). Emerald Publishing.
- Javed, M., Rashid, M. A., & Hussain, G. (2016). When does it pay to be good? A contingency perspective on corporate social and financial performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 133, 1062–1073.
- Khan, M. I., & Banerji, A. (2016). Corporate governance and foreign investment in India. *Indian Journal of Corporate Governance*, 9(1), 19–43. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0974686216635786>
- Love, I. (2011). Corporate governance and performance around the world: What we know and what we don't. *The World Bank Research Observer*, 26(1), 42–70.
- Malikov, R., Demirbag, M., Kuvandikov, A., & Manson, S. (2021). Workforce reductions and post-merger operating performance: The role of corporate governance. *Journal of Business Research*, 122, 109–120.
- Nguyen, C. T., Nguyen, L. T., & Nguyen, N. Q. (2022). Corporate social responsibility and financial performance: The case in Vietnam. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2022.2075600>
- Onaolapo, A. R., & Kolawole, S. A. (2019). Corporate characteristics and audit fees: Evidence from distributive firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. *The Interface*, 3(1), 1–13.
- Reverte, C., Gómez-Melero, E., & Cegarra-Navarro, J. G. (2016). The influence of corporate social responsibility practices on organizational performance: Evidence from eco-responsible Spanish firms. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 112, 2870–2884.
- Sameer, I. (2021). Impact of corporate social responsibility on organization's financial performance: Evidence from Maldives public limited companies. *Future Business Journal*, 7(29). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-021-00075-8>
- Zhang, J., & Ziyang, L. (2023). Impact of corporate social responsibility on financial performance and brand value of listed Chinese companies. *Sustainability*, 15(24), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152416864>
- Zhao, X., Chen, S., & Xiong, C. (2016). Organizational attention to corporate social responsibility and corporate social performance: The moderating effects of corporate governance. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 00(00).